

Impacts of Climate Change on Food Production in the Context of Population Growth: A Case Study of East Timor

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Abstract

Climate change is recognized as a global challenge; however, for developing countries such as Timor-Leste, its impacts are particularly severe relative to their limited economic capacity to adapt. The continuous growth of the population, coupled with a decline in food production, further exacerbates the country's vulnerability. Therefore, this study aims to examine the impact of climate change on food production in the context of a steadily increasing population, using a comprehensive review of existing literature. Ultimately, the study seeks to develop a model that illustrates the interrelationships between climate change, the decline in food production, emigration trends, rising food insecurity, and increasing dependence on imports.

Keywords: Climate change, food production, population increase, Timor-Leste.

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1. Introduction

Climate change is having, and will continue to have, significant impacts on the biogeochemical cycles of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), which have collectively contributed to the increase in global temperatures since pre-industrial times [9] [14]. Between 2011 and 2020, global surface temperatures continued to rise [18].

Timor-Leste, also known as East Timor, is located within the transitional biogeographical region of Wallacea [1] and covers approximately 15,000 square kilometers, including the Oe-Cusse Enclave, which occupies 815 square kilometers [5, 19]. The country has a long history of Portuguese colonization and Indonesian occupation [21]. As a developing nation, Timor-Leste is highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change [2]. The vulnerability of a system to climate change is determined by its level of exposure, its physical and environmental sensitivity, and its capacity and opportunity to adapt [3].

According to the World Meteorological Organization [31], Timor-Leste has already experienced, and is expected to continue experiencing, climate-related events such as increasing ocean heat content, sea level rise, ocean acidification, and global mean surface temperature rise—all of which may contribute to food insecurity. The Government of Timor-Leste, through its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) for 2022–2030, has identified rising average temperatures, biodiversity loss, sea-level rise, increased drought frequency, and greater variability and intensity of rainfall as key climate risks directly affecting the economy, livelihoods, and agricultural productivity.

The relationship between population growth and climate change has been widely studied, revealing a complex and multidimensional interaction [13] [16] [20]. Molyneux et al. [22] examined the linkages between climate change and population growth in Timor-Leste and their implications for food security. Furthermore, the IPCC [17] reported that increases in anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions have been driven largely by both economic and population growth.

These facts suggest that climate change poses a significant challenge for East Timor, particularly as the population continues to grow each year while national food production declines. The primary sector, agriculture, is increasingly affected by

climate change, which in turn exacerbates issues across other sectors of the economy.

2. Methods

The method employed in this research is a literature-based study, which involves a comprehensive review of existing research related to population dynamics and climate change adaptation within the agricultural sector. The aim is to develop an understanding of the potential implications of these factors for future food production in Timor-Leste. Ultimately, the study seeks to construct a conceptual model illustrating how climate change can lead to interconnected challenges such as emigration, public health issues, and increased dependence on food imports.

3. Results and discussion

Between 2014 and 2022, the population of Timor-Leste increased at an annual growth rate of 1.8%, reaching approximately one million people [27]. In 1999, around 76% of the population resided in rural areas, and 81% were engaged in agriculture-related work [11]. According to the Agricultural Census in 2019 [24], there were 141,141 registered farming households, and the total area of all agricultural holdings, including homesteads, was 216,200 hectares. These figures indicate that the majority of Timor-Leste's population continues to depend heavily on the agricultural sector, even as the population steadily grows.

Reflecting this dependence, the Government of Timor-Leste allocated USD 46 million to agriculture and food security in 2024, noting that the agriculture, forestry, and fisheries sectors collectively grew by 5% in 2022 [25]. However, the 2025 General State Budget report shows a decline in budget allocation—from USD 43.7 million approved in 2024 to a proposed USD 31.2 million for 2025, representing a reduction of approximately 29%. Similarly, the budget dedicated to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 2 (ending hunger, achieving food security, improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture) decreased slightly from USD 40.1 million to USD 40 million.

For over a decade, the agricultural sector has contributed approximately 23% of Timor-Leste's total non-oil real GDP. However, the 2021 Labor Force Survey indicated a decline in agricultural

employment—from 51% in 2010 to 31% in 2021 [30]. Climate projections further suggest that this sector may face increasing challenges in the coming decades. By 2030, the average temperature in Timor-Leste is expected to rise by 0.7°C, with projected increases of 0.8°C under a low-emission scenario and up to 2.2°C under a high-emission scenario by 2050. Annual rainfall variability is also expected to range from -15% to +11% by 2030, and from -13% to +8% under low emissions, or -25% to +21% under very high emissions, by 2070 [10]. Such changes may exacerbate the decline of the agricultural sector and threaten national food security and coffee exportation which a significant source of livelihood for almost 20% of Timor-Leste households [8].

Rapid population growth not only places pressure on economic growth but also contributes to rising youth unemployment. As Binswanger-Mkhize [7] suggests, agricultural development presents an opportunity to generate employment for rural youth and to reduce the pace of urban migration. The United Nations Department of Economic and Social

Affairs [29] recorded an increase in emigration from Timor-Leste after 2005, with consistent growth between 2010 and 2020. The main destinations for emigrants have included Indonesia, Australia, the United Kingdom, and Portugal. More recently, the Timor-Leste Population and Housing Census [27] reported that most emigrants are young people, with the top six destination countries being the United Kingdom, Ireland, South Korea, Australia, Indonesia, and Portugal. According to the Australian Department of Employment and Workplace Relations [4], the number of Timorese workers participating in seasonal and temporary labor programs in Australia has continued to increase, with many recent graduates taking part in half- or full-season employment.

Figure 1: The spend on food importation is continuing to rise since year 2018.

Source: The 2022 East Timor External Trade Statistics.

With the declining of food production in agriculture sector, caused more dependence on food imports from others countries, the numbers of budged spend for importation always increase from 2018 to 2022 [12]. The declining of food production because of climate may become hotter, drier, and variable arise through an increase in diseases, resulting in secondary malnutrition [6] [22] [28] [23], made the government has to spend more [26]. East Timor's 2025 general state budget allocates US\$99.2 million directly to the health sector compare that in 2025 was allocated US\$66.2 million [15].

Image 2: Model of how climate change accompanied by population growth caused decrease of food production and these lead to emigration, health issues and dependence of food importation.

Source: Author

The model suggested the declining of food production is driving by the continues impacts of climate change, in other context the population is continuing to growth, this lead to emigration, increase of health issues and country's foods importations dependence.

4. Conclusions

Projections for Timor-Leste indicate that climate change in the near future may lead to a further decline in food production due to its adverse impacts on the agricultural sector. This decline is expected to coincide with continued population growth, exacerbating pressure on food systems. As agriculture becomes less reliable for sustaining food production, increased dependence on imported food

could further weaken domestic agricultural productivity. Such conditions may also contribute to higher rates of emigration, worsening public health issues—including malnutrition—and deepening the country's reliance on food imports.

These challenges compel the government to allocate substantial financial resources each year to mitigate the effects of the nation's limited adaptive capacity. Strengthening cooperation with developed countries is therefore essential for enhancing Timor-Leste's resilience to climate change. Furthermore, financial support from developed nations—whose historical emissions have contributed significantly to global climate change—is vital to help vulnerable countries like Timor-Leste adapt to its impacts and address the resulting socioeconomic consequences.

References

- [1] ADB.(2014).*State of The Coral Triangle:Timor-Leste*.Asian Development Bank.ISBN 978-92-9254-527-7.
- [2] ADB.(2021).*Climate Risk Country Profile; Timor-Leste*.World Bank Group & Asian Development Bank.
- [3] Adger, W. N., Huq, S., Brown, K., Conway, D. Hulme, M.(2003).*Adaptation to climate change in developing world*. Progress in Development Studies.
- [4] Australian Government. Department of Employment and Workplace Relations.(2025).*Report on workplace safety initiatives*.
<https://www.employment.gov.au/reports/2025-safety-report>.
- [5] Jannisa, G. (2013). *Timor-Leste in the world: BC to Independence*. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1343692/FULLTEXT01.pdf>.
- [6] Barnett, J., Dessai, S., & Jones, R. N. (2007). Vulnerability to climate variability and change in East Timor. *AMBIO: a Journal of the Human Environment*, 36(5), 372-378.
- [7] Binswanger-Mkhize, H. P. (2009, June). Challenges and opportunities for African agriculture and food security. In *FAO Expert meeting on How to feed the World in (Vol. 2050)*.

- [8] Chain, T. L. S. C. V. (2024). Assessment Report of the Impact of Climate Change on on Timor Leste's Coffee Value Chain. *Australia Pacific Climate Partnership Support Unit*.
- [9] Ciais, P., C. Sabine, G. Bala, L. Bopp, V. Brovkin, J. Canadell, A. Chhabra, R. DeFries, J. Galloway, M. Heimann, C. Jones, C. Le Quéré, R.B. Myneni, S. Piao and P. Thornton, (2013). *Carbon and Other Biogeochemical Cycles*. In: Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.
- [10] CSIRO and SPREP (2021). 'NextGen' Projections for the Western Tropical Pacific: Current and Future Climate for Timor-Leste. Final report to the Australia-Pacific Climate Partnership for the Next Generation Climate Projections for the Western Tropical Pacific project. Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) and Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP), CSIRO Technical Report, Melbourne, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.25919/tgrj-6e56>.
- [11] Da Cruz.(2016). Food security in Timor Leste through crop production . *Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research*. Nesbitt H., Erskine W., da Cruz C.J. and Moorhead A. (eds). Proceedings of TimorAg2016, an international conference held in Dili, Timor-Leste, 13–15 April 2016. ACIAR Proceedings No. 146: Canberra. 187 pp.
- [12] Direção geral de Estatística.(2022). *External Trade Statistics 2022*.Ximenes, E. M., Moreira, L. de J., Gusmão, C., Lopes, S., Mendes, H., H.(ed.). DGE.
- [13] Dodson, J. C., Dérer, P., Cafaro, P., Götmark, F.(2020). Population growth and climate change: Addressing the overlooked threat multiplier. *Science of the Total Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141346>.
- [14] Galloway, J. N., W. H. Schlesinger, C. M. Clark, N. B. Grimm, R. B. Jackson, B. E. Law, P. E. Thornton, A. R. Townsend, R. Martin.(2014).Ch. 15: *Biogeochemical Cycles. Climate Change Impacts in the United States: The Third National Climate Assessment*, J. M. Melillo, Terese (T.C.) Richmond, and G. W. Yohe, Eds., U.S. Global Change Research Program, 350-368. doi:10.7930/J0X63JT0.
- [15] Governo de Timor-Leste.(2024, 27th of November). *2025 General State Budget Law Enacted: Commitment to Sustainable Development and the Welfare of the Population*. URL : <https://timor-leste.gov.tl/?p=41036&n=1&lang=en#:~:text=In%20health%2C%20the%20budget%20allocates,for%20old%20age%20and%20disability>.
- [16] Henderson, J. V., Jang, B. Y., Storeygard, A., Weil, D., N.(2025). Climate Change, Population Growth, And Population Pressure.*National Bureau of Economic Research*.
- [17] I P C C (2014). Climate change 2014 synthesis report. *IPCC*. Geneva, Szwitzerland, 1059, 1072.
- [18] IPCC.(2023) Sections. In: *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Core Writing Team, H. Lee and J. Romero (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, pp. 35-115, doi: 10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647.
- [19] Jannisa, G. (2019). *Timor-Leste in the world: BC to Independence*.
- [20] Madise, N. J., Dodoo, N. D., Mushomi, J. A., Mankhwala, C. S.(2024). Understanding the complex relationship between population and climate change mitigation. *Vienna Yearbook of Population Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1553/p-624f-7c9a>.
- [21] McWilliam, A., Traube, G., & Andrew McWilliam, E. (2011). *Land and life in Timor-Leste: Ethnographic essays* (p. 264). ANU Press.
- [22] Molyneux, N., da Cruz, G. R., Williams, R. L., Andersen, R., Turner, N. C.(2012).Climate change and population growth in Timor-Leste: Implications for food security. *Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences*. DOI 10.1007/s13280-012-0287-0.

- [23] Ramos-Horta, J., Karunakara, U., & van de Pas, R. (2025). Progress needed on climate and health goals, Timor-Leste. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 103(5), 287.
- [24] Republic Democratic of East Timor.(2020). *Timor-Leste Agriculture Census 2019*. General Directorate of Statistics, Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries.
- [25] Republic Democratic of East Timor.(2023).*Orçamento Geral do Estado 2024*. Parlamento Nacional. Díli. Timor-Leste.
- [26] Saikia, U., & Hosgelen, M. (2010). Timor-Leste's demographic destiny and its implications for the health sector by 2020. *Journal of Population Research*, 27(2), 133-146.
- [27] Timor-Leste Population and Housing Census.(2022).*Migration Summary of the Analytical Report*.Republica Democratica de Timor-Leste.
- [28] Twigg, M. (2017). Adapting to Food Insecurity in Timor-Leste. *The state of environmental migration*.
- [29] United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2020). *International Migration 2020 Highlights*(ST.ESA/SER.A/452).
- [30] World Bank Group.(2023).*Timor-Leste Economic Report;Rebalancing Priorities to Harvest Prosperity*. World Bank Group.
- [31] World Meteorological Organization,(2025). *State of the Global Climate 2024*. WMO. Switzerland. ISBN 978-92-63-11368-5.